

Evaluation of Avusor Pasture in the Eastern Black Sea Region of Türkiye in terms of Yield and Quality

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Abstract

This two-year study (2023-2024) investigated the nutritional characteristics of Avusor Pasture, located in the Çamlıhemşin district of Rize province in the Eastern Black Sea Region of Türkiye. Plant samples were collected from 12 different locations within the pasture during July of each year. Forage quality was assessed by analyzing crude protein (CP), acid detergent fiber (ADF), neutral detergent fiber (NDF), acid detergent protein (ADP), and mineral content (P, K, Ca, Mg) using a NIRS instrument. Nutritional parameters, including digestible dry matter (DDM), dry matter intake (DMI), relative feed value (RFV), digestible energy (DE), and metabolizable energy (ME), were calculated. The average dry matter yield (DY) was 118 kg da⁻¹. The average CP content was 17.03%, while ADF and NDF averaged 32.86% and 66.03%, respectively. The average RFV was 89.40, indicating moderate forage quality. Mineral concentrations were within typical ranges for pastures. Interannual variations were observed, particularly in CP content. The results suggest that Avusor Pasture provides a valuable forage resource for livestock, although interannual variability should be considered in grazing management. Further research on botanical composition and long-term grazing effects is recommended.

Research Article

Article History

Received :12.11.2024
Accepted :27.12.2024

Keywords

Rize
avusor pasture
forage quality
nutritional value
yield

1. Introduction

Feed costs constitute a substantial operational expenditure in livestock production, with pastures representing the most cost-effective source of roughage for sustainable farming practices. Globally, pastures account for approximately 70% of livestock roughage intake (Lund, 2007). The increasing global population, coupled with the escalating challenges posed by climate change and economic volatility, is placing unprecedented demands on the availability of high-quality roughage from these land resources. However, the conversion of pasturelands to alternative land uses and the widespread issue of overgrazing are significantly impacting the productive capacity of these vital natural resources.

Overgrazing is a key factor contributing to pasture degradation, particularly in arid and semi-arid environments (Snyman, 2005; Holechek et al., 2011). This degradation manifests as reduced pasture productivity, deterioration of soil physical and chemical properties (Beukes and Cowling, 2003), and heightened susceptibility to soil erosion. Moreover, overgrazing can promote the proliferation of undesirable plant species, diminish plant cover, and ultimately lead to biomass reduction (Tongway et al., 2003; Çomaklı et al., 2012).

For successful livestock production, both the quantity and quality of roughage obtained from pastures are essential (Heitschmidt et al., 1995). Consequently, sustainable pasture management necessitates adherence to robust management principles. The protection of existing pasture ecosystems and the implementation of rehabilitation initiatives in vulnerable areas are paramount. Achieving these goals requires a comprehensive evaluation of current pasture conditions and the factors contributing to their degradation. A detailed analysis of pasture vegetation is crucial prior to the development or implementation of any rehabilitation strategy. Therefore, before initiating rehabilitation activities, it is essential to determine the botanical composition, yield, and quality

attributes of different pasture sections, especially those exhibiting variations in soil properties, topography, and plant cover. This information enables the development and implementation of targeted rehabilitation practices (Kökten and Tükel, 2009; Kökten et al., 2010; Çınar et al., 2014; Alay et al., 2016; Çağan et al., 2016; Çağan and Kökten, 2019; Seydoşoğlu and Kökten, 2019; Seydosoglu et al., 2019; Seydoşoğlu and Başbağ, 2024).

Several studies have investigated the impact of various factors on pasture yield and quality. For instance, Öner (2016), in a study conducted at 2400 m altitude in the Palandöken pastures of Erzurum province, Türkiye, found that dry matter yield was 134.83 kg da⁻¹ in ungrazed areas and 68.21 kg da⁻¹ in grazed areas. Crude protein content was also higher in ungrazed areas (12.89%) compared to grazed areas (11.59%). Furthermore, analysis of Neutral Detergent Fiber (NDF) and Acid Detergent Fiber (ADF) content revealed lower values in ungrazed plots (NDF:56.01-57.04%; ADF:36.53-39.90%) compared to grazed plots. Sürmen and Kara (2018) examined the effect of slope on pasture yield in Aydın province, Türkiye, analyzing five different slopes (2%, 8%, 15%, 25%, and 30%). They reported dry matter yields ranging from 114.54 kg da⁻¹ to 223.03 kg da⁻¹, with the highest yield observed on the 8% slope. The highest NDF content was found in pastures with a 30% slope, while the lowest was observed on the 2% slope. The highest crude protein content (10.64%) was recorded on the 8% slope, and the highest Relative Feed Value (RFV) (101.35) was found on the 2% slope. Similarly, Severoğlu (2018) demonstrated the significant influence of slope on forage quality parameters, observing a decline in quality with increasing slope. In this study, dry matter yield was 56.43 kg da⁻¹, crude protein content was 8.14%, ADF content was 45.11%, and NDF content was 64.30%. The botanical composition was found to be 32.12% grasses, 25.28% legumes, and 42.60% other plant families.

This study aims to assess the livestock potential of Avusor Pasture, situated within the Çamlıhemşin district of Rize province in

Türkiye's Eastern Black Sea Region, by analyzing the nutritional value and mineral composition of its vegetation. Precise determination of plant composition and nutrient content is essential for the sustainable use of pasturelands and effective animal nutrition. To this end, comprehensive nutrient and mineral analyses was performed on collected plant samples. The resulting data is expected to provide valuable insights for informing and improving pasture management strategies specific to the Avusor Pasture.

2. Material and Methods

This research was conducted in Avusor Pasture, located in the Çamlıhemşin district of Rize province, a region celebrated for its natural beauty within the Eastern Black Sea Region of Türkiye. The study site is situated at an approximate altitude of 2550 meters above sea level and is located approximately 29 km from the district center. The research period spanned the years 2023 and 2024. The geographical location of the study area is

depicted in Figure 1, while representative photographs of the site are presented in Figure 2. Avusor Pasture serves as a prominent example of the characteristic pasture ecosystems found within this region.

Soil samples from Avusor Pasture were analyzed to determine key physical and chemical properties. The analysis revealed a clay-loam soil texture with a saturation percentage of 66.0%. The soil exhibited a moderately acidic reaction with a pH of 4.71. The total salt content was low (0.13%), indicating minimal salinity issues. The lime content was also low (0.11%). The organic matter content was classified as medium (2.41%). Available phosphorus (P_2O_5) and potassium (K_2O) levels were also found to be medium, with values of 5.42 kg da^{-1} and 46.16 kg da^{-1} , respectively. Long-term meteorological data analysis reveals that Rize province experiences an average annual temperature of $14.5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and an annual total precipitation of 2300 mm (Anonymous, 2025).

Figure 1. Location of the study area on the map (Google Earth)

Figure 2. Some photos taken from the study area

Plant material was collected from twelve distinct, different locations within Avusor Pasture during July of both 2023 and 2024. Vegetation was harvested at ground level using 50x50 cm quadrats. Fresh weights of the collected samples were measured *in situ* using a portable precision balance. Samples were then oven-dried at 70 °C for 48 hours to determine dry weights, which were subsequently converted to yield per unit area (kg da^{-1}). The dried plant material was ground and homogenized using a mill equipped with a 1 mm sieve. The concentrations of crude protein (CP), acid detergent fiber (ADF), neutral detergent fiber (NDF), acid detergent protein (ADP), and the minerals phosphorus (P), potassium (K), calcium (Ca), and magnesium (Mg) were determined using a Foss NIRS systems Model 6500 Win ISI II v1.5 NIRS instrument.

Nutritional parameters, including dry matter intake (DMI), digestible dry matter (DDM), relative feed value (RFV), digestible

energy (DE), and metabolizable energy (ME), were calculated based on ADF and NDF values using established equations from the literature: Digestible Dry Matter (DDM) = $88.9 - (0.779 \times \%ADF)$ (Oddy et al., 1983); Dry Matter Intake (DMI) = $120 / (\%NDF)$ (Sheaffer et al., 1995); Relative Feed Value (RFV) = $(DDM \times DMI) / 1.29$ (Sheaffer et al., 1995); Digestible Energy (DE) = $0.27 + 0.0428 \times (\%DDM)$ (Fonnesbeck et al., 1984); Metabolizable Energy (ME) = $0.821 \times DE$ (Mcal kg^{-1}) (Khalil et al., 1986).

Furthermore, Ca/P and K/(Ca+Mg) ratios were calculated to assess the relationships between macro element concentrations. Descriptive statistical analyses were performed on the collected data for all examined parameters. The JMP statistical software package was utilized to calculate descriptive statistics, including means, standard deviations, and ranges for each parameter.

3. Results and Discussion

The nutrient composition of grass samples collected from Avusor pasture during the two-year study period is presented in Table 1. These

data offer a comprehensive overview of the pasture's nutritional quality and highlight potential interannual variations in nutrient content.

Table 1. Yield and nutritional value of Avusor Plateau pasture

Features Analyzed	1.Year	2.Year	Average
Fresh Yield (FY) (kg da ⁻¹)	672±35.19	628±18.14	650
Dry Matter Yield (DY) (kg da ⁻¹)	120±12.26	116±6.55	118
Crude Protein (CP) (%)	18.74±2.28	15.32±1.64	17.03
Acid Detergent Fiber (ADF) (%)	31.20±3.38	34.52±7.62	32.86
Neutral Detergent Fiber (NDF) (%)	65.36±3.46	68.70±5.49	66.03
Acid Detergent Protein (ADP) (%)	1.04±0.06	1.08±0.09	1.06
Digestible Dry Matter (DDM) (%)	64.20±2.63	62.01±3.64	63.30
Dry Matter Intake (DMI) (%)	1.89±0.11	1.75±0.14	1.82
Relative Feed Value (RFV)	94.84±9.42	83.96±10.19	89.40
Digestible Energy (DE) (Mcal kg ⁻¹)	3.03±0.11	2.92±0.09	2.98
Metabolic Energy (ME) (Mcal kg ⁻¹)	2.49±0.09	2.40±0.11	2.45
Phosphorus (P) (%)	0.35±0.06	0.29±0.04	0.32
Potassium (K) (%)	2.10±0.25	1.85±0.19	1.98
Calcium (Ca) (%)	1.17±0.07	1.25±0.10	1.21
Magnesium (Mg) (%)	0.18±0.04	0.21±0.09	0.20
Ca/P	3.34±0.47	4.31±0.69	3.83
K/(Ca+Mg)	1.56±0.07	1.27±0.03	1.41

Table 1 presents the nutrient composition of grass samples collected from Avusor pasture over a two-year period. These data provide valuable insights into the overall nutritional quality of the pasture and potential interannual variations in nutrient content.

Fresh yield (FY) was measured at 672 kg da⁻¹ in the first year and 628 kg da⁻¹ in the second year, with an average FY of 650 kg da⁻¹. Dry matter yield (DY) was 120 kg da⁻¹ in the first year and 116 kg da⁻¹ in the second year, averaging 118 kg da⁻¹. These minor differences in yield values may be attributed to variations in annual climatic conditions or grazing intensity.

Crude protein (CP) content decreased from 18.74% in the first year to 15.32% in the second year, with an average CP content of 17.03%. This decrease may be influenced by differences in plant growth stage or environmental factors. Acid detergent fiber (ADF) and neutral detergent fiber (NDF) values averaged 32.86% and 66.03%, respectively. ADF and NDF are crucial parameters affecting forage digestibility and

animal intake. Acid detergent protein (ADP) averaged 1.06%.

Digestible dry matter (DDM) averaged 63.30%, dry matter intake (DMI) averaged 1.82%, relative feed value (RFV) averaged 89.40, digestible energy (DE) averaged 2.98 Mcal kg⁻¹, and metabolizable energy (ME) averaged 2.45 Mcal kg⁻¹. These values indicate the forage's potential to provide energy and nutrients for animals. The RFV value of 89.40 suggests a moderate forage quality.

The macro element analysis revealed average concentrations of phosphorus (P) at 0.32%, potassium (K) at 1.98%, calcium (Ca) at 1.21%, and magnesium (Mg) at 0.20%. These mineral concentrations are crucial for evaluating the nutritional adequacy of the pasture for grazing livestock. The phosphorus content (0.32%) is generally considered adequate for most grazing ruminants, although specific requirements may vary depending on the animal's physiological state. Potassium levels (1.98%) are well above the recommended requirements for livestock, indicating a sufficient supply of this essential

macro element. Calcium concentration (1.21%) is also considered adequate for most grazing animals, contributing to bone health, muscle function, and other physiological processes. Magnesium content (0.20%) is within the range typically considered sufficient for grazing livestock. The Ca/P ratio averaged 3.83, and the K/(Ca+Mg) ratio averaged 1.41. These ratios should be evaluated in terms of mineral balance. While a Ca/P ratio between 2:1 and 7:1 is considered ideal, the obtained value of 3.83 falls within this range.

Examination of the data in the table reveals certain interannual differences, particularly in CP and some mineral contents. These differences may be attributed to factors such as annual precipitation, temperature, plant growth stages, and soil properties.

The present study's findings on Avusor Plateau pasture provide valuable insights when compared with previous research. The average dry matter yield (118 kg da⁻¹) observed in our study is lower than the values reported by several researchers. For instance, Öner (2016) found higher dry matter yields in Erzurum's Palandöken pastures (134.83 kg da⁻¹ in ungrazed and 68.21 kg da⁻¹ in grazed areas). Similarly, Sürmen and Kara (2018) reported yields ranging from 114.54 to 223.03 kg da⁻¹ in Aydın, with the highest yield on 8% slopes. Altınok (2015) also documented higher yields (352.3 kg da⁻¹ in protected and 253.5 kg da⁻¹ in grazed areas) in spring-grazed meadows. However, our results are more aligned with Severoğlu (2018), who reported a lower yield of 56.43 kg da⁻¹. These differences in dry matter yield can be attributed to variations in environmental conditions (altitude, climate, soil type), grazing management practices, and botanical composition across the study locations. Çaçan et al. (2014) also found varying dry matter yields (203.70 kg da⁻¹ in protected and 106.85 kg da⁻¹ in grazed areas), highlighting the impact of grazing on yield. Nadir et al. (2012) reported somewhat higher dry matter yields (244.08-276.05 kg da⁻¹) in Tokat, further emphasizing the influence of regional and management differences. Regarding forage quality, our study's average

crude protein content (17.03%) is notably higher than the values reported by Öner (2016) (12.89% in ungrazed and 11.59% in grazed areas), Sürmen and Kara (2018) (maximum 10.64%), Severoğlu (2018) (8.14%), Altınok (2015) (8.29% in ungrazed and 8.35% in grazed areas), Çaçan et al. (2014) (19.69% in protected and 15.40% in grazed areas), and Taşdemir (2015) (maximum 12.2%). Nadir et al. (2012) found similar crude protein values (16.48-18.81%) to our findings. Kaplan et al. (2013) reported a wide range of crude protein (10.25-21.33%) in legume forages in Kayseri, indicating the potential for high protein content in specific plant species. The ADF (32.86%) and NDF (66.03%) values in our study are generally comparable to or slightly higher than those reported by Öner (2016) (NDF: 56.01-57.04%; ADF: 36.53-39.90%), Altınok (2015) (ADF: 36.95-36.72%; NDF: 55.98-56.82%), Taşdemir (2015) (ADF: 34.0-37.0%; NDF: 49.0-56.0%), and Nadir et al. (2012) (ADF: 24.38-26.84%; NDF: 34.59-36.32%). Severoğlu (2018) reported higher ADF (45.11%) and NDF (64.30%) values, while Çaçan et al. (2014) found lower ADF (29.48% in protected and 37.76% in grazed areas) and NDF (43.31% in protected and 50.86% in grazed areas) values. Kaplan et al. (2013) also reported a broader range for ADF (25.40-36.53%) and NDF (28.68-43.68%) in legume species. These variations in fiber content likely reflect differences in plant species composition, maturity stage at harvest, and environmental conditions.

The higher crude protein content observed in our study suggests a potentially higher nutritional value of Avusor Plateau pasture compared to some other regions. However, the slightly higher NDF values could indicate a lower digestibility. It is important to consider the combined effects of these parameters along with other factors like mineral content and botanical composition to fully assess the forage quality and its suitability for livestock production. The comparison with previous studies underscores the importance of site-specific management practices and further research to optimize pasture utilization and improve livestock productivity.

4. Conclusion

This two-year study (2023-2024) assessed the nutritional characteristics of Avusor Pasture, situated in the Çamlıhemşin district of Rize province, Türkiye, within the Eastern Black Sea Region. The analysis of plant samples collected during July of each year provided valuable insights into the pasture's forage quality and its potential contribution to livestock production. The average dry matter yield (DY) over the two years was 118 kg/da, demonstrating a moderate level of biomass production. This yield, while representing a valuable forage resource, highlights the need for careful grazing management to ensure sustainable utilization of the pasture. The average fresh yield (FY) was significantly higher at 650 kg da⁻¹, indicating the substantial water content of the forage at the time of sampling. These yield parameters provide a baseline for assessing the pasture's carrying capacity and inform decisions regarding stocking rates and grazing rotations. Interannual variations were observed in some parameters, particularly in CP content, which decreased from 18.74% in the first year to 15.32% in the second year. This fluctuation underscores the influence of environmental factors, such as precipitation, temperature, and solar radiation, on forage quality. Such interannual variability emphasizes the importance of adaptive grazing management strategies that consider seasonal and yearly changes in forage nutritional value. The observed CP levels, coupled with other nutritional parameters, position Avusor Pasture as a potentially valuable resource for supporting livestock production in the region. Overall, the findings of this study demonstrate that Avusor Plateau provides a valuable forage resource for livestock in the Eastern Black Sea Region of Türkiye. The pasture offers a moderate to good nutritional profile, although interannual variability should be considered in grazing management practices. Further research is recommended to investigate the long-term effects of grazing pressure and climate change on the pasture's productivity and nutritional quality. Additionally, studies focusing on botanical composition and its

relation to forage quality would provide a more comprehensive understanding of the pasture ecosystem. This information can be used to develop sustainable grazing management strategies that optimize livestock production while preserving the ecological integrity of Avusor Plateau.

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To Cite

Çatal, M.İ., 2025. Evaluation of Avusor Pasture in the Eastern Black Sea Region of Türkiye in terms of Yield and Quality. *ISPEC Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 9(2): 331-339.
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14970143>.
